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THE CULTURAL-HISTORICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND DEVELOPMENT DYNAMICS OF THE 20TH-CENTURY GANJA LITERARY ENVIRONMENT IN AZERBAIJANI LITERATURE

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Ganja is one of the most ancient centers of culture in Azerbaijan. Historians have confirmed that Ganja existed long before the Common Era and have written extensively about its material and cultural monuments. Ganja represents one of the regions embodying Azerbaijan's material and spiritual identity, where heroes have shown courage and sacrificed their lives for the country's freedom and independence. It is not by chance that the proclamation of Azerbaijan as an independent state is associated with the name of this city: in 1918, the Azerbaijani National Council and Government were transferred from Tbilisi to Ganja, where they temporarily operated. Ganja is among the oldest centers of culture, art, and science in Azerbaijan. The great poet Nizami Ganjavi lived here, becoming a source of pride for the entire East and world literature. Poets such as Mahsati Ganjavi, Abul-Ula Ganjavi, and Givami Mutarrizi, who lived in the same century, also played an important role in the second half of the 12th century in the history of Azerbaijani literature. In subsequent centuries, this literary environment continued to expand its influence, entering new stages of development. Notably, the first literary assembly in Azerbaijan – *Divani-hikmat* (1820) – was founded in Ganja under the guidance of the eminent poet Mirza Shafi Vazeh, who united poets and lovers of literature both in Ganja and in Tbilisi.

The establishment of around twenty branches of the Union of Azerbaijani Writers, both within and outside the country, primarily aims to foster the development of literature in the regions. The very first of these branches was founded in Ganja. In the 1920–1950 s, the literary milieu of Ganja produced a number of talented figures whose works went beyond the city's borders and enriched the «Ganja page» of Azerbaijani literature.

Key words: Ganja, Azerbaijan, antiquity, culture, literature, history, poetry.

Introduction. Located on both banks of the Ganja River, in the Ganja–Gazakh plain in the northeastern part of the Lesser Caucasus, this ancient city is the second largest in Azerbaijan by area. Its advantageous geographical position on the Silk Road made Ganja a center of art, trade, and literary activity throughout the Near East and an object of interest for foreign conquerors. The history of Ganja is exceptionally ancient; historians and writers have produced numerous articles and books about it. Russian scholar M.M. Altman, in his scientific essay *The History of the City of Ganja*, provides valuable historical and archaeological data, noting that ancient burials and kurgans confirm the existence of settlements here. Archaeological excavations have revealed Bronze Age (1st millennium BCE) artifacts made of black clay, as well as bronze swords, arrows, bracelets, and beads. The discovery of burials from later periods also proves that cultural life continued to develop in this area.

According to Altman, «Ganja was known as *Janza* in Arabic, and as *Ganja* in Persian and Azerbaijani» [1; 5–6]. From early times, the arts flourished in the city, and Ganja craftsmen became famous throughout the Near East. In the 11th century, Ganja became the capital of the Shaddadid state; city walls and fortifications were built to defend against foreign invaders.

During both the Shaddadid and Atabey periods, Ganja developed into a true Eastern city. Particularly under the Atabeys, artisans, musicians, physicians, and engineers received special patronage. The Ganja Library (*Dar al-Kutub*) was renowned throughout the East. The presence of such a rich temple of books undoubtedly contributed to the flourishing literary atmosphere of the 12th century. Yet one of the city's most unforgettable historical symbols is the *Gate of Ganja* – carried off to Georgia by King David IV. This symbol has found poetic expression in Aydin Murovdaghli's poem «The Gate of Ganja», where it becomes a metaphor for longing and poetic grief:

*Once the invading army struck at your might,
The gate lost its memory in the fight.
Perhaps it's the wing of the Simurgh in flight –
It longs to gaze upon Karabakh's light,
To clash with lightning and ignite!* [2; 20].

The story of the master blacksmith Ibrahim Osmanoglu, who forged the city's legendary gates, still captures popular imagination. During the earthquake and subsequent looting by Georgian forces, this work of art was taken to Georgia. In *Ganja and the Ganja People*, Ahmad Isayev recounts legends about the origins of many of the city's historical monuments, such as the Hard Rock, the Maiden Tower, and the Roman Cemetery. The 1139 earthquake of Ganja was not legend but fact: «The Ganja earthquake gave the

world a double miracle – the creation of the beautiful, blue-eyed Lake Goygol and, soon after, the birth of the sun of poetry, the immortal Nizami» [3; 33].

A popular uprising against foreign occupation took place in Ganja in 1231, led by the craftsman Usta Bandar – a hero who has not been forgotten through the centuries. Writer and publicist Ahmad Isayev devoted his novel *Rebellion* to this episode, which was warmly received by readers. However, his best-known work remains *Ganja and the Ganja People* (1998), republished three times (most recently in 2002). He wrote: «This city has a strange fate. Neither the origin of its name nor the date of its foundation is known. I turned the pages of many books, read chronicles, consulted sources, yet found no single opinion. Each offers a thousand conjectures, a thousand hypotheses. How then are we to know the truth?» [3; 19].

In the 19th century, when Ganja served as a provincial center (*Elisavetpol*), the city had its own emblem, and during the rule of Javad Khan, the Ganja Khanate flew a flag bearing distinctive symbols. Despite periods of invasion by Arabs, Persians, Georgians, and Russians, Ganja preserved its grandeur. Many historical monuments still stand, attracting not only locals but also visitors: the Ganja Divankhana, the Tomb of Jomard the Butcher, the building of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic, the Chokak Bath, the European-style bathhouse, the Alexander Nevsky Church, and numerous mosques such as Bagmanlar, Qazakhlar, Khalfali, Molla Jalilli, Ozan, Sofulu, Shahsevan, Sharefkhanli, Zarrabi, Qizil Hajili, as well as caravanserais of Ugurlu Khan and Shah Abbas, the house of Alekber bey Rafibeyli, the Ganja Men's Gymnasium, the Real School, the St. Nina Girls' Gymnasium, the house of Ismayil bey, the Domed House, the city's underground passages, and the Bottle House – all reflecting the unity of antiquity and modernity.

Doctor of Philology Ali Salahaddin, in his monograph dedicated to Javad, introduces Ganja to readers as follows:

«Since ancient times, Ganja has been the land of the *Dede Qorqud*, *Koroglu*, *Gurbani*, and *Asli and Karam* epics – the cradle of countless myths, legends, and tales; the homeland of Mahsati, Abul Ula, Nizami, Dede Yedyar, Dede Kerem, Shamama Beyim, Mirza Shafi, and many other poets and musicians. Surrounded by the Goshgar, Kepez, and Murov mountains, between the Shamkir, Goshgar, and Kurek rivers, Ganja has stood proudly on the Ganja River. Because it sacrificed martyrs resisting invading armies, it is called the city of Imam Hussein. Monuments such as Jomard Qassab, Imamzada, and Shah Abbas Mosque remain as lasting symbols. Ganja also gave the world heroes like Bandar, Javad Khan, and in our time, Israfil» [4; 26].

For centuries, Ganja has played an exceptional role in the development of Azerbaijani art and culture, particularly in shaping its literary and intellectual life. Among the many figures associated with this magnificent city, the genius of Nizami Ganjavi stands foremost – not only as the pride of Ganja and Azerbaijan but of the entire Eastern and world literary heritage. The birth of the Azerbaijani Renaissance is closely connected with his creative legacy. Across centuries, the poetic flame kindled by Nizami in the 12th century has never been extinguished; it burns ever brighter. Visitors to this ancient yet modern city first encounter his mausoleum, a symbol of enduring cultural memory.

As the eminent critic Yashar Garayev wrote:

«Long before Shakespeare, we encounter the triumphs of Renaissance thought in Nizami. The *social utopia* expressed in Nizami Ganjavi's *Iskandarnama* may be regarded as the embodiment of a Renaissance ideal elevated to the level of a concept of 'social beauty'» [5; 28–29].

Drawing on Ganja's deep historical and cultural roots, scholars have continually emphasized the richness and antiquity of its literary heritage. The national poet Mammad Araz, recognizing Nizami as a hero of thought, wrote:

*Wherever the winds may drive me astray,
My golden dawn of poetry hides away.
If Nizami still walks upon this earth,
His thought alone keeps the world in sway.* [6; 309].

The decision of National Leader Heydar Aliyev to commemorate the 840th anniversary of Nizami Ganjavi's birth, as well as the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, proclaiming the year 2021 as the «Year of Nizami», once again demonstrates that Nizami's art is immortal and eternally relevant.

The literature of twelfth-century Azerbaijan also produced such prominent figures as Abul-Ula Ganjavi, Mahsati Ganjavi, and Qivami Mutarrizi, contemporaries of Nizami who lived and created in Ganja. The name of Ganja appears in one of Mahsati's rubaiyat, which indicates that as early as the twelfth century, Ganja was already recognized as a flourishing center of poetry, culture, and art. In one of her exchanges with her beloved – later her husband – Amir Ahmad, the son of the Khatib of Ganja, Mahsati wrote: «You said: In Ganja you shall find joy fulfilled – Here I am, here you are, behold – this is Ganja!» [3; 48]

The fact that such eminent figures as Nizami, Abul-Ula Ganjavi, Qivami Mutarrizi, and Mahsati left behind a rich literary legacy demonstrates the deep historical roots of Ganja's cultural and literary traditions, which have been shaped over the centuries.

The renowned publicist Ahmad Isayev's book *Ganja and the People of Ganja* draws attention with its wealth of historical and cultural facts about the city's past and present. Isayev writes:

«The Iranian historian Mirkhwand connects the foundation of the city with the name of the Sassanid ruler Qubad I, who lived in the fifth century. The fourteenth-century historian Hamdallah Qazvini claims that Ganja was built in 659–660. Other sources also exist. *Derbendnameh* reports that 'Ganja existed at the end of the seventh and the beginning of the eighth centuries. Recall the tomb of Jomard the Butcher – a relic of the seventh century! A silver dirham minted in Ganja in 712–13 is preserved in the Hermitage Museum in St. Petersburg.' And what about the Imamzade Mausoleum? According to experts, it dates back to 739. Thus, a city must have existed here – one that minted its own coins, built cemeteries, and erected tombs and mausoleums that have survived to the present day» [3; 19].

Based on historical sources and written records, it may be concluded that the ongoing cultural and historical processes contributed to Ganja's emergence as a prominent center of science and culture throughout history.

In the same book, the chapter devoted to the history of the Ganja Khanate is of particular importance, as it systematically presents facts and materials about Ganja's past for the first time. One of the key figures in *Ganja and the People of Ganja* is Javad Khan, portrayed not only as a historical leader but also as a beloved literary character. The author introduces previously unknown facts about Javad Khan's life to Azerbaijani readers, thereby enriching the nation's historical consciousness [3; 188–214].

Throughout history, Ganja has produced many heroes, poets, and artists who have contributed to the spiritual and intellectual development of Azerbaijan. Among these distinguished figures are Mirza Adigozal Bey, author of *Karabakh-nameh*; Mirza Mehdi Tabib Ganjavi (the poet known under the pseudonym «Naji»); Asgar Agha Gorani, the first actor to perform Haji Gara on the Azerbaijani stage; and members of the Sheikhzamanov family, descendants of Sheikh Ibrahim Qudsi from Nizami's lineage. Another eminent figure, «the father of the people of Ganja», Alakbar Bey Rafibeyov, became known throughout Azerbaijan for his nobility and moral virtues. Even the great poet Ahmad Javad, who lived in Ganja for a period, expressed admiration for Rafibeyov.

The chapter «*The Road Rising from Ganja*» in Isayev's book draws attention with rich factual material about the early twentieth century, up to 1920, highlighting the sociopolitical developments that took place in the city. As the author notes:

«For many years Ganja was called the 'nest of the Musavat Party,' the 'cradle of nationalism'; its name was even changed to 'Kirovabad» [3; 260]

Ganja is a land that reflects the natural beauty of Azerbaijan. Providence has spared nothing in bestowing its grace upon this city. Its plane trees, verdant parks, alleys, beautiful and elegant buildings, and its harmonious blend of tradition and modernity form Ganja's unique and picturesque identity. Hundreds of poems and dozens of songs have been dedicated to Ganja. The national poet Rasul Rza's poem «*Ganja*» evokes deep pride:

«Your name endures in history, my Ganja, O Ganja!

Year by year, you have grown, O Ganja!

Never have you bowed your head to strangers –

Proud forever you stand, O Ganja!» [7; 289].

The poet also depicts the city's old and new neighborhoods – Bala Bagman, Boyuk Bagman, Sofulu, Zarrabi, Shahsevan, Ozan, Imamli, Yeni Irevan, Attarlar, Mollajalilli, and Kilsekend – each with its own distinctive history and identity, as ancient as the city itself.

The continuation of Ganja's literary tradition in the nineteenth century was marked by the establishment of the first literary society in Azerbaijan – *Divani-Hikmat* (1820–1830), led by Mirza Shafi Vazeh (1794–1852). Founded in Ganja, and later continued in Tiflis after Mirza Shafi's relocation there, the society gathered poets and intellectuals from both cities. Among its members were Mirza Shafi Vazeh, Abbasgulu Agha Bakikhanov, Mirza Mehdi Naji, Mirza Fatali Akhundov, Sheikh Ibrahim Qudsi (Naseh), Agha Ismayil Zabih, Mirza Yusif Vidadi, Fazil Khan Sheyda, Haji Yusif Qane, I. I. Grigoriev, G. Rozen, L. Z. Budagov, and F. Bodenstedt. *Divani-Hikmat* continued its activities until the deaths of Mirza Shafi (1852) in Tiflis and Mirza Mehdi Naji (1882) in Ganja [8; 9–30].

One of the society's poets, Molla Abbas Shole, wrote a ghazal with the refrain «Ganja», one of the earliest poems in Azerbaijani literature dedicated to praising the city:

«Spring has come – how wondrous the season of Ganja,

Its markets filled with milk and cream of Ganja.

Once turmoil ruled this city's every lane,

But now the plane trees bloom in Ganja's gardens» [8; 29].

The early, mid-, and late twentieth centuries marked a vibrant period for the literary milieu of Ganja.

Eminent poets and writers such as A. Jafaroglu, S. Vurgun, A. Javad, M. Jalal, N. Rafibeyli, A. Jamil, A. Ziyatay, Z. Khalil, N. Hasan-zade, and N. Babayev all lived and created in Ganja, contributing significantly to the formation of its cultural and intellectual atmosphere.

This was further affirmed by National Leader Heydar Aliyev in his address about Ganja:

«At the beginning of the twentieth century, and especially during the 1930s and 1940s, the majority of our scholars and cultural figures either originated from Ganja or began their intellectual and literary activity there» [3; 351]

It is well known that a certain period of Ahmad Javad's life was closely connected with Nizami's homeland – Ganja. He lived in the city between 1906–1919 and 1930–1934, years that left an indelible mark on both his life and creative work. In his poems dedicated to Ganja, Javad vividly evokes the city's natural and spiritual beauty – its landscapes, resources, and surroundings such as Hajikand, Khoshbulag, and Aharja:

«Beloved Ganja stands,
Like Sheki, Shirvan – Ganja stands.
The world knows we are apart,
Yet love endures till death» [9; 561].

The poet's love for Ganja is vividly reflected in the following poem: *In 1906, I came to Ganja, in the Year of the Horse.*

*I mounted Dilboz,
Crossed plains and gray steppes.
My heart remained in Shamkir,
My father moved with me,
Neither I slept, nor he found rest* [9; 378].

A poem written by Ahmad Javad in 1911, «*You are a Caucasian, Love the Caucasus*», is considered one of the earliest valuable examples of socio-political lyricism in his creative work. S. Ibrahimli also emphasizes his deep affection for Ganja and refers to Javad's verses devoted to the city:

*For five years I walked and rejoiced in your gardens,
Never had my fill of your water, Ganja.
You are the one who brought me this sweet sorrow,
I am indebted to you—shall I repay it, Ganja?!* [9; 400].

Between the 1960 s and 2000 s, the literary milieu of Ganja was enriched by poets such as Farida Aliyarbeyli, Mammad Alim, Khazangul, Bahadur Ferman, Aydın Murovdaghli, Sahib Ibrahimli, Inqilab Isaq, Rubail, Alesker Elioglu, Alemzar Alizadeh, Huseyn Hatemi, Nizami Aydın, and Mezahir Huseynzadeh. From the 1960s onward, their works, resonating beyond Ganja, expressed themes of freedom, love, and patriotism in Azerbaijani literature.

Among the many poems inspired by Ganja, Inqilab Isaq's «*My Ganja*» (1998) stands out for its original metaphors and lyrical imagery that go beyond mere praise:

*I said «Ganja»... and my word smiled,
This name shines brighter than the sun.
Its plains, its land of youth,
Are touched by the divine hand* [9; 63].

Ganja has inspired numerous symbolic landscapes – Kəpəz, Qoşqar, Göygöl, the plane trees, and more. Among Ganja's literary figures, Aydın Murovdaghli distinguishes himself through both productivity and civic sensitivity. In his works, Ganja's national and historical identity becomes at once a source of pride and moral strength. It must be particularly emphasized that Aydın Murovdaghli is one of the most talented poets to have written profoundly moving verses about Ganja and its immortal genius, Nizami.

*Ganja is eternal through history and time,
Rising from itself to greater heights!
Ganja is a monument to Nizami's spirit,
Even the waters have written its name in their depths – Bathe this city in golden light!* [10; 43].

In the poetry of Ganja's poets, Azerbaijan's oldest and most beautiful city occupies a special place. There is hardly a poet from Ganja who has not dedicated at least one poem to the city. Among them, the poetic cycle by Farida Aliyarbeyli stands out. Her 1970 poem «*My Ganja*» expresses her poetic spirit with precision, creating a bridge between Ganja's past and its present:

*My people, my land are heroic,
They stood bravely before their foes.
My young Israfil went to war,*

Returned with a star shining on his chest [11; 16–17].

Farida Aliyarbeyli's poems written in the 1960s and 1970 – «*Spring in Our Ganja*», «*A Girl from Ganja*», «*A Guest from Ganja*», «*Where Have the Birds Gone*», «*Ballad of the Plane Tree*», and «*Mount Murov*» – all reflect Ganja's presence in Azerbaijani poetry. Her poem «*The Kahriz*» (1990) is also devoted to Ganja. In this work, she recounts the story of Haji Mir Gasim, a respected 19 th–20 th century philanthropist who provided water to the people of Ganja by channeling it from the springs of Qizilqaya. The kahriz flowed along Zarrabi Street, bringing life to the people and to the century-old plane trees:

*Zarrabi is Ganja's ancient street,
Along its path the plane trees line—
Adorning the city with their grace,
By day they shade, by night they shine,
The plane trees are Ganja's first lovers* [11; 69].

In her poem «*Spring in Our Ganja*» (1963), Farida Aliyarbeyli links the beauty of spring with the joyful spirit of her native city:

*Spring is a lovely season,
In every land, in every place.
But there is a special charm,
In our own beloved city* [11; 4].

In Huseyn Hatemi's «*Plane Trees of Ganja*», nature is interwoven with history. The plane trees of Ganja are portrayed as carriers of poetic and historical memory, their grandeur compared to the arms of Babak Khorramdin:

*The plane trees of Ganja,
As grand as our forefathers,
Filled with remembrance,
They are the arms of my Babak –
The plane trees of Ganja* [11; 17].

The poetic environment in Ganja has always been characterized by continuity and harmony. Throughout different historical periods, many talented representatives of Azerbaijani poetry have lived and created in this region, ensuring that the candle once lit by the great Nizami never went out. The Ganja branch of the Union of Writers of Azerbaijan has consistently supported the creative endeavors of poets living in the city.

Many poets residing in Ganja and its surrounding districts have earned recognition and admiration not only in this region but throughout Azerbaijan. Ganja has given to the world of Azerbaijani literature and culture such prominent poets and writers as Nizami Ganjavi, Mahsati Ganjavi, Abul-Ula Ganjavi, Dede Yedyar, Dede Kerem, Shamama Beyim, Mirza Shafi Vazeh, Nigar Rafibeyli, Alekber Ziyatay, Zeynal Khalil, Jahanbakhsh Javadzadeh, Altay Mammadov, Farida Aliyarbeyli, Aydın Murovdaghli, Alesger Elioglu, Bahadur Ferman, Mammad Alim, Sahib Ibrahimli, Khazangul, Nizami Aydın, Alemzar Alizadeh, Inqilab Isaq, Fazil Senan, Nushaba Asad Mammadli, Murshud Mammadov, Rubail Allahverdiyev, and Huseyn Hatemi. The city has also produced distinguished scholars and intellectuals such as Hamid Arasli, Ahmad Jafaroghlu, Akbar Babayev, Rustam Rustamzadeh, Khalil Yusifli, Sabir Aliyev, Jalil Naghiyev, Tofiq Malilki, and Nureddin Babayev.

The history of the national theater in Ganja dates back to 1895. This theater became the cradle of many actors who later gained prominence in Azerbaijani cinema and performing arts, including Mammadraza Sheikhzamanov, Alekber Seyfi, Adil Isgandarov, Ashraf Yusifzadeh, Suleyman Taghizadeh, Ramziya Veysalova, Mammad Burjaliyev, Aladdin Abbasov, Ibrahim Hamzayev, Zulfuqar Baratzadeh, and Sadaya Mustafayeva.

When we look at the general panorama of Ganja in the 1930–1960 s, we observe a number of significant historical facts: the opening of the Shura Collective Farm Market in Ganja (1932); the Kirovabad district's leadership in the struggle for high cotton yields (1935); delivery of 4,328 tons of cotton by collective farms to procurement centers (1935); extensive urban greening efforts by the Stalin and Nizami Executive Committees (1951); the staging of M.S. Ordubadi's *Foggy Tabriz* at the State Drama Theatre (1951); regulation of the city's water supply system (1953); preparations by the Pioneers' House for the 750th anniversary of Nizami Ganjavi's death (1953); completion of a new canteen for workers of the Textile Combine (1955); the establishment of a new residential district three kilometers from the city center (1959); and the opening of a new, elegant House of Culture at the Nizami Grape-Growing State Farm (1960). In the 1980 s, a new atmosphere began to emerge in Ganja. Notable events of this period include the erection of a monument to Mahsati Ganjavi (1983), the administrative division of the city into two districts (1984), the inauguration of a new cinema-concert hall on the left bank of the Ganja River (1985), and the international tour of the *Göygöl* State Song and Dance Ensemble in Mexico (1988). All these developments marked significant progress in the city's cultural life.

Finally, the restoration of the city's historical name – *Ganja* – and the launch of the newspaper *Gəncənin Səsi* («The Voice of Ganja») symbolized the dawn of a new era. Indeed, the year 1990 is regarded as the beginning of a new chapter in the city's modern history.

The frequent official visits of National Leader Heydar Aliyev, President Ilham Aliyev, and First Vice-President Mehriban Aliyeva to Ganja have greatly contributed to the city's dynamic development. By the 2000 s, Ganja had transformed into not only one of the most developed cities of Azerbaijan but also one of the most modern and rapidly progressing cities in Europe.

Significant cultural activity was observed during this period. The opening of the memorial museum of the distinguished writer Mir Jalal Pashayev, the grand celebration of his 100th anniversary in Ganja, the youth festival dedicated to the 870th anniversary of Nizami Ganjavi, the publication of new books on Nizami's life and work by the Ganja City Executive Authority, the staging of new performances by the Nizami Poetry Theater, the organization of the international scientific-practical conference «*Nizami and World Literature*», the presentation of Mirza Shafi Vazeh's literary heritage in Ganja, and the opening of a branch of the Miniature Book Museum – all these and many other events further strengthened Ganja's image as a vibrant cultural center.

Each historical visit by President Ilham Aliyev to Ganja has marked the beginning of new achievements and further economic, social, and cultural progress for the city. In accordance with the decrees of President Ilham Aliyev, large-scale construction and restoration works continue to this day: new industrial enterprises, parks, and boulevards are being established, and the city is developing at a rapid pace. The constant attention and care of the President are deeply felt in the ancient and historic city of Ganja.

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КУЛЬТУРНО-ІСТОРИЧНІ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ТА ДИНАМІКА РОЗВИТКУ ЛІТЕРАТУРНОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА ГЯНДЖІ ХХ СТОЛІТТЯ В АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНСЬКІЙ ЛІТЕРАТУРІ

Гульнар Гусейнова САФДАР – викладач кафедри азербайджанської та світової літератури,
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Гянджа є одним із найдавніших центрів культури Азербайджану. Історики підтвердили, що Гянджа існувала задовго до нашої ери, і багато писали про її матеріальні та культурні пам'ятки. Гянджа є одним із регіонів, що втілюють матеріальну та духовну ідентичність Азербайджану, де герої проявили мужність і пожертвували своїм життям за свободу та незалежність країни. Не випадково проголошення Азербайджану незалежною державою пов'язане з назвою цього міста: у 1918 році Національна рада та уряд Азербайджану були переведені з Тбілісі до Гянджі, де вони тимчасово діяли. Гянджа є одним із найстаріших центрів культури, мистецтва та науки Азербайджану. Тут жив великий поет Нізамі Гянджаві, який став джерелом гордості для всього Сходу та світової літератури. Такі поети, як Махсаті Гянджаві, Абул-Ула Гянджаві та Гівамі Мутаррізі, що жили в тому ж столітті, також відіграли важливу роль у другій половині XII століття в історії азербайджанської літератури. У наступні століття це літературне середовище продовжувало розширювати свій вплив, вступаючи на нові етапи розвитку. Примітно, що перше літературне зібрання в Азербайджані – Дівані-хікмат (1820) – засновано в Гянджі під керівництвом видатного поета Мірзи Шафі Вазе, яке об'єднало поетів та любителів літератури як у Гянджі, так і в Тбілісі. Створення майже двадцять відділень Спілки письменників Азербайджану, як у країні, так і за її межами, має на меті, перш за все, сприяння розвитку літератури в регіонах. Перше з цих відділень засновано в Гянджі. У 1920-1950-х роках літературне середовище Гянджі дало низку талановитих діячів, чий творчий внесок вийшов за межі міста та збагатили «Гянджинську сторінку» азербайджанської літератури.

Ключові слова: Гянджа, Азербайджан, античність, культура, література, історія, поезія.

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